

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF CAMPRISTIC PEDAGOGY IN TRAINING FUTURE TEACHING STAFF

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Abstract: In this thesis, the nature of campristic pedagogy and its importance in the process of training future pedagogic personnel are explained. The concept of camprist pedagogy is considered as an integrated pedagogical approach to the modern educational process, and its positive results in the educational process are analyzed. The thesis also analyzes the main principles and methods of the camprist approach in improving the professional qualifications of pedagogical personnel and preparing them for effective pedagogical activities in the future. On a scientific basis, educational and didactic possibilities of this pedagogy, as well as recommendations for practical application have been developed.

Key words: Campristic pedagogy, future pedagogical personnel, educational process, pedagogical approach, didactic opportunities, professional qualification, pedagogical training, innovative methods.

Introduction.

The current process of globalization and rapid changes in the education system require new approaches to the process of training future pedagogues. The role of innovative pedagogical approaches in increasing the efficiency of the educational system, as well as in the formation of qualified pedagogues suitable for socio-economic and cultural needs, is incomparable. From this point of view, camprist pedagogy is relevant in the educational process today and offers an approach aimed at comprehensive development of pupils and students.

Campristic pedagogy is based on the integration of various disciplines, and it attaches great importance not only to the acquisition of theoretical knowledge, but also to the formation of practical skills. This approach is an important factor in training future pedagogues, developing their professional competence, mastering innovative technologies, and forming a creative approach.

This thesis examines the main principles, content and practical importance of camprist pedagogy. Attention will also be paid to the problems that arise in the process of applying this approach to the training of future pedagogues and ways to solve them. At the same time, its role and importance is based on the

example of positive results from the experience of using camprist pedagogy in the educational system.

One of the main tasks of the modern education system is to equip future pedagogues not only with theoretical knowledge, but also to develop their abilities to conduct practical activities, solve problem situations, and adapt to the needs of modern society. From this point of view, camprist pedagogy is important as a current approach in the field of education.

Campristic pedagogy is aimed at comprehensive development of students by combining interdisciplinary approach and innovative methods. The main principles of this pedagogy provide for the creation of an interactive and cooperative learning process between the teacher and the student. Therefore, it is necessary to apply a camprist approach in the field of education for the following reasons:

The need for interdisciplinary integration. It is not enough to study pedagogical knowledge only in the theoretical framework; by connecting them with other subjects, students' ability to see problems from different perspectives is developed. For example, the connection of pedagogy with psychology, technology, and culture increases the effectiveness of education.

Introduction of innovative technologies. Modern educational institutions require mastering of modern technologies. Campristic pedagogy allows for the integration of innovative approaches to the educational process, in particular, digital tools, interactive teaching methods and multimedia technologies.

Personalized education. Campristic pedagogy supports person-oriented education. This approach ensures the organization of the educational process taking into account the individual needs, abilities and characteristics of students.

Formation of professional competencies. Future pedagogues should have professional competencies that meet the needs of modern society. Campristic pedagogy plays an important role in this process, as it develops students' abilities to think creatively, solve problems and perform innovative activities through a practice-oriented approach.

Modernization of educational content. In modern education, instead of abstract theoretical approaches, programs based on practice, relevant to current and changing needs are needed. Campristic pedagogy appears as an effective tool in the modernization of educational content.

The use of camp-based pedagogy in the educational process is not only limited to the development of professional training of future pedagogues, but it also serves to improve the overall quality of education. The pedagogues formed

through this approach will be not only highly qualified specialists, but also socially responsible, creative and able to apply modern pedagogical methods in practice. Therefore, camprist pedagogy is taking an increasingly important place as an integral part of the educational process.

Literature analysis.

Scientific resources on the theory and practice of camprist pedagogy play an important role in the development of new pedagogical approaches aimed at increasing the effectiveness of the educational process. National and foreign researches on this topic are aimed at integrative approaches, formation of interdisciplinarity and application of innovative technologies in the educational process.

In foreign literature, campist pedagogy is considered as a method that emphasizes the development of skills and competencies in students based on an interdisciplinary approach. For example, in the works of J. Devey[2] and L. Vygotsky[6], the importance of integrated education in the development of independent thinking in students was noted. These theories are the basis for creating a multi-dimensional learning environment that meets the individual needs of students.

In the researches of national scientists, in particular, unique approaches in the educational system of Uzbekistan were analyzed. Researchers such as O. Jorayev[3] and M.N. Normurodov[4] emphasize the harmonization of national values and modern educational technologies in the training of future pedagogues as the main priority of camprist pedagogy.

In addition, the work of J. Bruner[1] on the "educational culture" defines the methodological foundations of the camprist approach, where special emphasis is placed on involving students in the active learning process and opening up their creative potential. Also, in the works of T. E. Kaganov [5], the methodical principles of camprist pedagogy based on the unification of different groups in the classroom and their mutual cooperation are important.

From the analysis of the above researches, it can be seen that camprist pedagogy is an effective way to develop not only theoretical, but also practical knowledge of students in the training of future pedagogues. At the same time, national and international experience shows the universality of this approach, as well as its adaptability to local conditions.

Based on the literature presented during the thesis, it is planned to analyze the application and effectiveness of camprist pedagogy in the pedagogical process on the example of practical experiences.

Discussion.

Campristic pedagogy has its place as an effective approach to combining theory and practice in the process of training future pedagogues. This approach, first of all, helps students to form interdisciplinary knowledge, to strengthen their theoretical knowledge with practical skills, as well as to improve the quality of the educational process through the use of innovative educational technologies.

One of the important aspects of this pedagogy is that it serves to develop not only the professional training of students, but also their social and personal competencies. For example, the camprist approach improves students' independent thinking, problem solving and creative approach skills by introducing problem situations into the learning process. Also, this approach allows students to develop teamwork skills, because one of the main principles of camprist pedagogy is based on group cooperation.

Research shows that the introduction of innovative technologies into the educational process with the help of campristic pedagogy increases the interest of students in classes and ensures their active participation. In particular, high efficiency is achieved in improving students' professional skills through the use of interactive methods, virtual environments and various simulations.

At the same time, a number of problems are observed in the process of practical application of camprist pedagogy. In particular, insufficient training of pedagogues on the application of this approach, lack of necessary innovative tools in the teaching process, and lack of suitable curricula for interdisciplinary integration are among the main obstacles. This prevents the full potential of camprist pedagogy to be demonstrated in practice.

In order to solve these problems identified during the discussion, first of all, it is necessary to prepare pedagogical staff to use modern approaches through training courses, provide educational institutions with technological equipment, and integrate the principles of camprist pedagogy into educational programs. At the same time, the creation of conditions that encourage active interaction between teachers and students also serves to increase the effectiveness of this approach.

The introduction of camp-based pedagogy in the educational process not only develops the professional competencies of future pedagogues, but also helps them to have flexible, creative and innovative thinking in the modern educational environment. Therefore, further study and development of this

approach will serve to significantly improve the quality of the education system in the future.

Conclusion.

In this study, the role and importance of camprist pedagogy in the training of future pedagogues was comprehensively analyzed. This approach has been found to be an important factor in improving the educational process in terms of quality, enriching students' knowledge theoretically and practically, as well as forming their professional competencies.

Campristic pedagogy implies the use of interdisciplinary integration and innovative technologies in the educational process. This serves to develop students' ability to think creatively, make independent decisions, and conduct pedagogical activities in line with the needs of modern society. Also, this approach helps to increase the educational and didactic potential of pedagogic personnel.

It is noted that the main problems identified during the research, including insufficient training programs and resources, insufficient knowledge and skills of pedagogues on the application of the camprist approach, serve as an obstacle to the full implementation of this approach. done. In order to eliminate these problems, it is necessary to improve the qualifications of pedagogical staff, provide technological support for the educational process, and widely introduce modern methods in classes.

In conclusion, it can be said that camprist pedagogy, as one of the innovative directions of increasing efficiency in the educational process, requires wider study and implementation in the future. The development of this approach creates conditions for adapting future pedagogues to the modern educational environment and providing them with quality educational services. Therefore, one of the important tasks is to develop a strategy to increase the role and importance of camprist pedagogy in the educational system.

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